

Parents' Strategy in Overcoming Children's Learning Difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency

Mansyur Suma¹

¹Islamic State University of Alauddin Makassar, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research aims 1) to reveal the role of parents in overcoming children's learning difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, and 2) to reveal what obstacles parents experience in overcoming children's learning difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency. This research used descriptive qualitative research which is located in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency. The research approach used is the guidance approach. The primary data source for this research is informant. Secondary data sources are books on parental strategies in educating children, parental guidance books, magazines, newspapers, the internet and other data sources that can be used as complementary data. The research instruments were interview guides, cameras, notebooks, pens, tape recorders. Furthermore, the data collection method used is observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis techniques were carried out through three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results of this research indicate that the role of parents in overcoming children's learning difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, namely firstly providing motivation in learning, secondly educating by always advising children, thirdly educating using exemplary methods, , fourth, providing learning facilities for children, fifth, parents as teachers at home. The obstacles faced by parents are first the parents' economy, secondly the lack of education and understanding of parents, thirdly children don't listen to what their parents say and environmental factors that are too free.

KEYWORDS-Brokerage, Parent's strategy, Mandar regency, Children, Learning difficulties.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a system, organized and bears a fairly broad mission, that is everything related to physical development, health, skills, thoughts, feelings, will, social up to matters of belief and faith (Van de Werfhorst & Mijs, 2010). It is associated with the rapid changes of today's era which greatly affect students in thinking and behaving, especially towards those who are in a stage of development in transition who are looking for self-identity (Ceka & Murati, 2016). Education means giving guidance or direction by someone to the development of others. Therefore, it is the most important thing in life to develop human qualities in order to achieve a better change and be ready to face life (Wilson, 2017).

According to Guryan et al., (2008) parents are the people who are most responsible for the process of fostering and educating children, from birth to adulthood because the family is the first school for children before they get education elsewhere. In addition, parents also have an obligation to meet the basic needs of

children which include physical-biomedical needs (care), emotional/love needs (love), and the need for mental stimulation for the learning process in children (Andini, 2017). The responsibilities of parents cover everything, both those related to those at home and outside, it is include physical and spiritual education, moral and intellectual development, and spiritual strengthening of children. Therefore it can be likened to the good and bad of a country very much depends on the success of parents in educating the children (Probert, 2009; Prihandoko et al., 2022).

In fact, there are still many parents who are not aware of their responsibility towards the education of their children. They are more concerned with the activities and routines they have as if they think that school is the only factor that determines their child's achievement without considering that they also have responsibility for their child's education (Essa & Burnham, 2019). In Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Chapter IV article 7 paragraphs 1 and 2 states that: "Parents participate in choosing educational units and obtain information about their child's development." Meanwhile, Article 7 paragraph 2 also states that "parents of children of compulsory education age are obliged to provide basic education to their children".

Educating children is a task that must be done by every parent, as the verse in QS. At-Tahrim/66: 6 :

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا قُوا أَنفُسَكُمْ وَأَهْلِيكُمْ نَارًا وَقُودُهَا النَّاسُ
وَالْحِجَارَةُ عَلَيْهَا مَلَائِكَةٌ غِلَاظٌ شِدَادٌ لَا يَعْصُونَ اللَّهَ مَا أَمَرَهُمْ
وَيَفْعَلُونَ مَا يُؤْمَرُونَ ﴿٦﴾

O ye who believe! Protect yourself and your family from the fires of hell whose fuel is humans and stones; guardian angels who are rough, and hard, who do not disobey Allah in what He commands them and always do what is commanded

This verse contains an order for believers to protect themselves and their families from the torments of hell fire. The command implies educating the family, including children, so it practice the teachings of the religion that already know. In addition, parents also guide the children to know more about religion outside the family and school environment, such as reciting the Qur'an with friends, reading religious books, and so on. Children must be accustomed in doing good things and leaving bad deeds. Parents who consciously educate their children will always be guided the children become independent, and well personality. Parents will reflexively to educate, being carers, guides, and coaches as teachers and leaders for the children.

Basically, parents have the responsibility for the education of the children because education from parents is the first and foremost for a child. Moreover, the family is a security provider, therefore parents have formally handed over their children to institutions, (schools), but parents still have the responsibility to supervise children at home, parents are not justified in handing over their children absolutely to schools (Jailani, 2014). This means that parents still have responsibility for education. Therefore, cooperation between the school and parents is needed in the formal education development because not all children's needs can be met.

While the implementation of education in our schools is generally only aimed at students with more abilities, so that students with mediocre or less abilities will be slightly ignored. Thus, students who are outside the more capable category (very weak and very stupid) do not get adequate opportunities to develop their abilities. Furthermore, it arises learning difficulties which not only affect students with low abilities, but also occurred by students with average abilities (Rahman, 2016). In addition, learning difficulties can also be experienced by students who are more capable because of certain factors that hinder the achievement of academic levels that are based on with expectations, the efforts and cooperation of teachers and parents in identifying what problems are the causes of learning activities so that they encounter difficulties. Parents are the key to children's success, especially in overcoming their learning difficulties at home. Likewise, teachers have

the right to know the level of learning difficulties of children at school.

Based on the observations in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, it is known that parents have played a significant role to overcome children's learning difficulties. The motivation given by parents only on financing and advice, but children's daily life still gets less attention because parents are busy to work as farmers so the facilities provided are inadequate and it is getting less attention from parents who are indifferent to study time, such as watching TV during study, using gadgets and playing with friends.

The interaction of parents and children is very influential in overcoming children's learning difficulties. However, many parents let their children play gadgets more and make children negligent in learning and addicted to gadgets (Gans & Silverstein, 2006). Based on the results of interviews conducted in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, the information was obtained that parents did not understand their child's condition, so parents need to evaluate children's conditions, formulate children's learning schedules, providing facilities, and reducing to allow using gadgets more.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The research objective in this research are 1) to reveal the role of parents in overcoming children's learning difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, and 2) to reveal what obstacles parents experience in overcoming children's learning difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency.

III. LITERARY REVIEW

Parents is a family component consisting of father and mother, and the result of a legal marriage bond and form a family. The parents in biological fathers and mothers in the family (Böök & Perälä-Littunen, 2008). According to Nightingale et al., (2019) the family is a center of affection and mutual help among others, and it has become very important as a child educator. Therefore, parents are most responsible for the education of their children. Family relationships with children usually involve elements of their parents, grandparents, siblings and extended family members (Perälä-Littunen & Böök, 2012). Based on the definition of parents that has been explained above, the researcher conclude that parents are two adults who live together in a legal and religious marriage bond so that they give birth to children or offspring.

The role of parents is a very important for children towards adulthood. Children are educated to be able to find self identity, so it given the opportunity to decide for profession that is occupied based on the expertise (Reed-Knight et al., 2014; Lanta, 2022). In this case the task of parents is to provide input, direction and consideration of the choices that have been made by children to become successful people. Parents also facilitate the need for children to achieve their goals such as meeting school needs and including tutoring when it is felt necessary for the child (Baez & Talburt, 2008; Hasnia et al., 2022). Based on the description above, it can be concluded that parents is the best place to carry out first education and the role of parents to children is as educators, protectors, caregivers, and role models for their children.

3.1 Factors Causing Learning Difficulties

Learning is a process that causes a change or renewal in behavior or skills. The success or failure of learning depends on various factors, while these factors can be divided into two groups based on Shaleh (2004):

a. Internal Factor

1) Physiological Factors

Children who are not healthy will have learning difficulties, because they are easily tired, sleepy, dizzy, lose concentration, lack of enthusiasm, disturbed mind. Because of these things, the acceptance and response of students is reduced, the nerves of the brain are not able to work optimally to process, manage, interpret and organize learning materials.

2) Psychological Factors

Psychological factors in learning difficulties is influenced by intelligence, talent, interest, motivation, mental health factors and special types of a student. In this case children who do not have a normal IQ, the lack of potential that children have in all fields that can make them lag behind, the absence of a child's interest in a subject which will cause learning difficulties, the lack of motivation they have to encourage it to be more active study.

b. External Factor

1) Family Factors

Family is the main and first center of education but it as a factor causing learning difficulties when parents pay less attention to the children's education, indifferent, do not pay attention to the children's learning progress, parents who are cruel, authoritarian which cause unhealthy mentality for children and causes learning difficulty (Jumiati et al., 2021).

2) Family Economic Condition

The cost factor is a very important because learning and continuity are very costly (Breuer & Wicker, 2008; Arniati et al., 2019). For instance to buy school supplies, school fees, and other costs. Poor families are also unable to provide adequate learning places.

c. Learning motivation

Motivation is the overall driving force within the child that is capable of causing learning activities which guarantees the continuity of learning activities and which gives direction to learning activities, so that the goals desired by the child's learning subjects can be achieved (Prihandoko et al., 2021). There is a driving force so that children can move based on the abilities to increase the power of the movement.

IV. METHOD

This research used qualitative research which is better known as naturalistic inquiry. Qualitative research is a contextual research that makes humans as instruments, and adapted to reasonable situations in relation to existing data collection is generally qualitative in nature (Wijaya, 2018).

V. RESULTS

5.1. Educational facilities and infrastructure in Galeso Village

Table 1. Number of the school facilities

Types	Number of School	Number of Teaching Staff	Number of Student
TK	1	9	27
SD	3	29	391
SMP	1	22	208

Source: Galeso Village Profile Book 2016

Table 2. Social Condition Graduated from School but did not continue

Types	Village1	Village2	Village3	Village4	Village5	Village6
SD	56	70	143	86	64	48
SMP	92	54	10	36	41	42
SMA	52	73	66	62	20	37
PT	34	31	2	18	7	-

Source: 2016 Galeso Village Profile Book

The livelihoods of most of the people of Galeso Village are dominated by farmers and fish farmers. The rest are students and people who have not working and there are youths who choose to migrate to other areas/urban areas. In addition there are also fishermen, entrepreneurs, civil servants, and carpenters.

Most of the families already have TV, radio, cellphone facilities which make the knowledge of the times grow faster. This is due to the fairly good distribution of PLN

Table 3. Telecommunications and information facilities

No.	Ward	Number of User
	Viilage	Electricity
1.	GalesoBarat	104
2.	GalesoUtara	145
3.	GalesoTengah	100
4.	GalesoTimur	118
5.	GalesoPatoreang	51
6.	GalesoTanjung	98

Source: 2016 Galeso Village Profile Book

The Role of Parents in Overcoming Children's Learning Difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency

Parents are the first people who play an important role in shaping the attitudes and behavior of children. Besides that, other family members such as grandparents, aunts, uncles or cousins certainly have a role in teaching, guiding and instructing children to do everything that allows children to interact and benefit their environment. Every parent certainly has a different strategy in providing guidance, especially in overcoming learning difficulties. The strategies used by parents based on the results of observations and interviews are as

follows:

a. Motivator

Motivation in learning activities is a force that can become energy for children. To utilize the potential that exists within him and the potential that exists outside of himself to demonstrate learning goals. Parents as children's motivators must provide encouragement in all children's activities, for example by giving prizes when children succeed in exams. The motivation given by parents will certainly make children more active in learning.

Data 1 Family 1

"As said by Mr. Arsyad and Mrs. Salmania as Rahmat's parents, one way to give motivation to their children is by giving praise. Mr. Arsyad and Mrs. Salmania said by giving praise for children's exemplary learning, it certainly makes the child's happy and feels appreciated for what he has done. So that children will do that behavior repeatedly because what they do is liked by many people. Children can also be given motivation, for example if the child ranks 1st, 2nd or 3rd in exams, it can be rewarded in the form of taking the child for a walk somewhere or giving him a gift. This motivation that given is strategy to make the child always gets grades at school"

This is in line with Rahmat's words that his parents, especially Mr. Arsyad, always give praise to their children when they successfully complete a job optimally. His parents also often give gifts or take him on trips to tourist attractions if he gets a ranking at his school. This is what motivates Rahmat to continue to be active and earnest in learning.

From the explanation above, it can be concluded that the strategy for overcoming children's learning difficulties is to provide motivation. The motivation can be in the form of giving compliments, taking them for a walk and giving gifts to children so that children feel happy and their mood becomes enthusiastic in learning.

b. Methods of Giving Advice/Exemplary

Giving advice or understanding to children about how to overcome learning difficulties, how to learn well certainly requires examples and role models from parents.

Data 2 Family 2

"Mrs. Warda said that my strategy as a parent is to always give advice to my child, whether it's in study or in everyday life. If there is no advised, today's children easily fall into unwanted things. In terms of learning I always accompany and give directions to my child. I always give good examples of exemplary behavior even though it is just small things like not throwing garbage anywhere, behaving well, not lying and always carrying out Allah's commands. My husband also does this, Mr. Yusuf always guides and fosters children towards a good, moral, and noble personality. The example of example that was instilled in Yusuf was such as taking him to pray at the mosque, teaching him to give alms by giving him money and then ordering him to fill the charity box, teaching him to be friendly and shaking hands with others after finishing the prayer.

This is also based on what was said by the son of Mr. Aslam Sulaiman, namely Muh. Abrizam

Data 3 Family 3

"My parents always advise me in studying, guide me and always accompany me in studying. If I do not study in a day, he advised me, if I do not understand the lessons my parents always guide and teach me.

Based on the statement above, it can be concluded that the role of parents in overcoming learning

difficulties is very necessary, namely by giving exemplary advice and providing examples to children in order to teach them directly.

c. Facilitator

The role of parents as facilitators, most parents have provided learning facilities such as books, stationery, internet quota, as well as cellphones. With facilities in the form of a comfortable place to study and adequate learning equipment, children will be more active and enthusiastic about learning.

Do not forget that parents also provide good nutrition so that children become healthy and develop properly. This is based on what Anita's mother said

Data 4 Family 4

"As a parent, I have provided learning facilities for my child Fatiha Auni Zakirah, such as cellphone, quotas, stationery, uniforms and so on. Since who else will give this if not us parents. I hope that by providing these learning facilities, children will be diligent in learning. As for nutrition, I don't pay much attention, in essence, every day I always provide food for our family, sometimes I also make cakes/snacks so that the children are more enthusiastic and healthy."

This is in accordance with what was said by Fatiha Auni Zakirah who stated that their parents had provided all the facilities in the form of stationery, school uniforms, quotas, cellphones and so on.

Data 5 Family 5

"Yes, my parents have provided learning facilities such as quotas, books and others. Before Covid-19, I didn't have a cell phone, but when school started going online, my parents bought me a cell phone to always take part in online learning. My parents always guide me to study, they always ask how was learning at school, whether I have homework. My parents also always accompany me in studying, unless he is busy sometimes I do my own homework, but every night my parents don't forget to check the homework that I did alone earlier."

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be seen that parents have tried their best to provide learning facilities and basic needs for children, so parents hope that their children can study hard and always be enthusiastic in pursuing their goals.

d. Parents as teachers at home

The role of parents as teachers at home is to provide a variety of information, provide positive ideas, guide, educate and control children's learning activities. Even though parents are busy they will always take the time to check the learning schedule and remind their children to study. Parents also have to accompany and guide them in the learning process and help their children when there is material that is difficult for them to understand.

Data 6 Family 6

"Ms. Ramlah, stated that at school I become a teacher to teach all students but at home I become a teacher for my children. Indeed, we parents are very busy taking care of the household and so on, but we must not forget to check the children's lessons, remind us if there are any assignments and always guide our children in learning. If I don't have time to teach my child Muhammad Fatih, I will order my older child to teach his younger sibling or replace me in guiding his younger sibling to study."

5.2. Obstacles Faced by Parents in Overcoming Children's Learning Difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency

Various ways are used by parents and other family members in educating children so that later they become pious, intelligent children and can make their parents proud. Every parent certainly has obstacles or obstacles in overcoming their child's learning difficulties. These obstacles can come from anywhere, both from parents, family or the child himself. Of course every family has its own way of overcoming these learning difficulties.

Based on the results of research through the process of observation and interviews, it can be seen that the obstacles faced by parents in overcoming children's learning difficulties are:

a. Education and Busy parents

In this case, not a few parents who do not understand their children's learning material. Although the majority of parents' education in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency is up to high school, but there are also parents whose education only reaches elementary or junior high school. From the results interview with Mr. Mansur said that:

Data 7 Family 7

"I rarely help or accompany children in learning, sometimes I feel confused and anxious if my child asks for an explanation regarding the material given by the teacher, because I don't understand the material. My education only reached junior high school, which is why I only told my children to study and continue studying so they wouldn't be like me. Sometimes I also ask his older brother or his aunt to teach him so he understands the lesson"

There are still parents who are rare in teaching or guiding children so it does not experience difficulties in learning. There are still parents who do not help their children in doing assignments, parents also don't ask whether the child has learning difficulties. This is because parents think that children can definitely do it because they have studied at school.

b. Parents' economy

The economic condition of each child's parents is different. In general, the economy of parents in rural areas is at the lower middle level. Therefore, children who live in rural areas tend to have lower academic achievement than students who live in urban areas, especially children whose parents have middle and upper economic backgrounds.

Children whose parents have middle to lower economic backgrounds tend to be less able to provide learning facilities for their children such as study books, cellphones and internet quota for studying. This will hinder the child's learning process. This is in accordance with what Nurjannah's mother said:

Data 8 Family 8

"My husband is just a farmer whose daily needs are just right for us to eat, so sometimes I feel sorry for my child, because I have not been able to provide good learning facilities. Like giving him a cell phone or internet quota. It is difficult for us to meet our daily needs"

c. Derived from the Child's Personal and Environment

The environment or place of residence greatly influences the attitudes and behavior of children because children really need peers to discuss or express their emotions. Children often go out to play if they are not supervised by their parents. In the learning process there are also children who are lazy and do not listen to their parents. In accordance with the words of the source, Mrs. Nasria said:

Data 9 Family 9

"Sometimes my child doesn't hear what I'm saying, I also wonder why he is

like that. He prefers to play HP, watch TV or play with his friends until he forgets the time. Today's children are very different from the children of the past. In the past, when our parents told us to listen, we were very obedient and respectful to our parents. But the child now always delays or says later until he doesn't carry out the parent's orders."

The statement above has proven that the lack of supervision in educating children makes Sihanak stubborn and difficult to manage. As well as the environment or association of children who are less controlled by parents, it makes children lazy in learning.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the descriptions in the previous chapters, in this chapter the researcher will present several conclusions from the results of this research including: 1) Parents' strategy in overcoming children's learning difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, namely that parents always educate, guide, give encouragement/motivate, provide all children's educational needs (facilitators) and control children, 2) the obstacles experienced by parents in overcoming children's learning difficulties in Galeso Village, Wonomulyo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, namely the parents' economy, lack of education and understanding of parents about educating children well, and children not listening to what parents say and environmental factors that are too free.

REFERENCES

- [1] Andini, C. (2017). *Children Emotion in The Movie" Big Hero 6"* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Islam Negeri Alauddin Makassar).
- [2] Arniati, F., Darwis, M., Rahman, N., & Rahman, F. (2019). Mother Behavior to Their Daughters As Seen in "Pride and Prejudice" and "Little Women". *ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 2(4), 620-625.
- [3] Baez, B., & Talburt, S. (2008). Governing for responsibility and with love: Parents and children between home and school. *Educational Theory*, 58(1), 25-43.
- [4] Bööck, M. L., & Perälä-Littunen, S. (2008). Children Need Their Parents More Than a Pizza in the Fridge! Parental responsibility in a Finnish newspaper. *Childhood*, 15(1), 74-88.
- [5] Breuer, C., & Wicker, P. (2008). Demographic and economic factors influencing inclusion in the German sport system—a microanalysis of the years 1985 to 2005. *European Journal for Sport and Society*, 5(1), 33-42.
- [6] Ceka, A., & Murati, R. (2016). The Role of Parents in the Education of Children. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(5), 61-64.
- [7] Essa, E. L., & Burnham, M. M. (2019). *Introduction to early childhood education*. Sage Publications.
- [8] Gans, D., & Silverstein, M. (2006). Norms of filial responsibility for aging parents across time and generations. *Journal of marriage and family*, 68(4), 961-976.
- [9] Guryan, J., Hurst, E., & Kearney, M. (2008). Parental education and parental time with children. *Journal of Economic perspectives*, 22(3), 23-46.
- [10] Hasnia, H., Andini, C., Tahir, M. D., Hunaeni, H., Zulfikariandi, Z., & Muslimin, M. T. (2022). The Ability of 1st Class Students of SMAN 11 Enrekang to Arrange Verbal and Nominal Sentences. *ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 5(3), 539-550.

-
- [11] Jailani, M. S. (2014). Teori pendidikan keluarga dan tanggung jawab orang tua dalam pendidikan anak usia dini. *Nadwa: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 8(2), 245-260.
- [12] Jumiati, Rahman, F., Lewa, I., Akhmar, A.M. (2021). The Potential of Children's Literature in Education and Environmental Ethics: Linguistic and Literary Approaches. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Published by Atlantis Press SARL.
- [13] Lanta, J., Rahman, F., Lewa, I., & Akhmar, A. M. (2022). Respect for Nature in Indonesian Children's Fiction: Ecocriticism Perspective. *Webology*, 19(1), 6010-6021.
- [14] Nightingale, R., McHugh, G., Kirk, S., & Swallow, V. (2019). Supporting children and young people to assume responsibility from their parents for the self- management of their long- term condition: An integrative review. *Child: care, health and development*, 45(2), 175-188.
- [15] Perälä-Littunen, S., & Böök, M. L. (2012). The Beginning and End of Parental Responsibility—Finnish Parents' Views. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 43(6), 925-941.
- [16] Prihandoko, L. A., Anggawirya, A. M., & Rahman, F. (2021). Students' Perceptions Towards Autonomous Learners Concept in Academic Writing Classes: Sequential Mixed-Method. *In International Joined Conference on Social Science (ICSS 2021)* (pp. 487-491). Atlantis Press.
- [17] Prihandoko, L. A., Al Ahmad, A. S. M., Fredy, F., & Rahman, F. (2022). Multi-Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing Perceived Academic Writing Competence (PAWC) of Vocational School Students. *OKARA: Jurnal Bahasa dan Sastra*, 16(2), 329-348.
- [18] Probert, R., Gilmore, S., & Herring, J. (Eds.). (2009). *Responsible parents and parental responsibility*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- [19] Rahman, F. (2016). The Strategy of Teaching Literature through Language-based Methods: A Communicative Approach. *In Annual Seminar on English Language Studies* (Vol. 1, pp. 156-170).
- [20] Reed-Knight, B., Blount, R. L., & Gilleland, J. (2014). The transition of health care responsibility from parents to youth diagnosed with chronic illness: a developmental systems perspective. *Families, Systems, & Health*, 32(2), 219.
- [21] Saleh, A. R. (2004). *Psikologi Suatu Pengantar Dalam Persepsi Islam*. Jakarta: Kencana
- [22] Van de Werfhorst, H. G., & Mijs, J. J. (2010). Achievement inequality and the institutional structure of educational systems: A comparative perspective. *Annual review of sociology*, 36, 407-428.
- [23] Wilson, E. (Ed.). (2017). *School-based research: A guide for education students*. Sage.
- [24] Wijaya, H. (2018). *Analisis data kualitatif ilmu pendidikan teologi*. Sekolah Tinggi Theologia Jaffray.